

THE IMPORTANCE OF ECONOMIC KNOWLEDGE IN TRAINING MODERN MEDICAL PERSONNEL

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Abstract. *The article describes the issues of the necessity of teaching the science of economic theory in order to acquire economic knowledge in the training of medical personnel in higher education at the present time.*

Keywords: *theory, economics, economic theory, higher education, medicine, qualified personnel.*

Introduction. In the concept of developing the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030, raising the process of training highly qualified personnel with independent thinking, modern knowledge and high moral and ethical qualities, raising higher education to a new level in terms of quality. for the purpose of development, it is planned to develop the social sphere and economic sectors on the basis of advanced educational technologies [1].

The Concept of the health care system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2019-2025 envisages: "Formation of an effective system of training, retraining and upgrading of medical personnel, development of medical science" [2].

At the present time, the requirements of the market economy require all its participants to acquire economic knowledge. However, our future personnel cannot ignore market relations in their activities. In this regard, every modern specialist should know economic relations in market conditions: market elements, economic categories and essence of laws, conditions of competition. So, economic knowledge is necessary for everyone today. Therefore, it is an urgent problem to teach the science of economic theory in the higher education system of our country, as well as for the training of highly qualified personnel with economic knowledge in the field of medicine. Research methodology. In the article, we considered the process of activation of economic knowledge acquisition and its management using historical, economic, logical principles, deterministic approach and discourse analysis method. Also, the methods of scientific abstraction, grouping, and systematic analysis were used in the implementation of research.

Literature review: It is known that future specialists are taught fundamental economic knowledge by the subject "Economic Theory". With the help of the ideological-educational function of the science of "Economic theory", students, experts form the worldview of economic students (modern economic thinking, modern market) [3.35].

In the scientific literature, the following scientific views can be found on the issue of the need to teach them economic knowledge in order to train highly qualified personnel in the medical field:

- in order to practice medicine effectively, doctors and medical workers need not only medical skills, but also economic knowledge [4].

- The article shows the role of economic knowledge in the socialization of future doctors. The case method is described as a form of activation of the teaching and learning process, and the advantages of the case technology compared to other methods in the study of economic theory at the medical university are considered. [5].

- Health economics is a science that is closely related to the fundamental principles of economic theory that studies the use of limited resources, the economic efficiency of public health protection measures, the organization and management of health care [6].

Taking this into account, we can say that we did not find a source about the relevance of this issue today in Uzbekistan. It is for this reason that the article is written.

Main part. It should be remembered that there are objective laws that express the essence of things and events in nature and society. The purpose of science is to discover, know, and consciously use these laws in practice. On the contrary, people go into the essence of natural and social phenomena and reveal the operation of certain laws. Similarly, thanks to the theory, we are talking about the nature of events and processes in economic life. Remember how many theories have been put forward in search of an answer to the question: if wealth is not given by God, then where does it come from? Many economic theories do not stand the test of practice and time. As for the reason for this, there are theories and laws that were once scientifically based, but with the passage of time and changing conditions, they do not correspond to the economic relations that exist between people and their interests. Because there is always progress in the history of human life, because the productive forces of society are growing.

A brief conclusion can be drawn: thanks to the theory, the essence of the phenomenon (process) is revealed, the law of action and the mechanism of its implementation are determined. For example, the process of commodity exchange, this phenomenon has long been the focus of scientists. In the end, the law of value was determined, which made it possible to reveal the essence of this phenomenon and determine the mechanism of its implementation.

Thus, thanks to the theory, the actions of economic laws are studied and determined, they have an objective nature, like the laws of nature, that is, they act independently of the will and consciousness of people. Their difference is that the objective nature of the laws of nature is more clearly manifested, and the economic laws are not so clear, but ignoring or underestimating them in economic activities will cause great harm to people.

And finally, we have arrived at the point of the "axis" of this article, and it should be noted that in this situation, economic theory in any life, or rather, economic knowledge to study a certain economy in different situations formation, that is, economic theory is needed. However, only this science is able to visually study the mechanism of economic development and solve the problems that have arisen. To visualize this more clearly, let's recall the tasks performed by economic theory.

Therefore, it is necessary to fully understand the necessity of economic theory in general development through the following functions:

1) the task of knowledge means that economic theory, like any other science, is of fundamental importance: it expands our thoughts about the world around us by researching the economic relations between people and events in society. Thanks to this, it is possible to fully understand the reforms being carried out in our country;

2) practical task - the main goal of practical economy - is to ensure economic development using limited resources effectively and to satisfy various growing needs based on this;

3) methodological task - the science of economics itself, methods of knowledge, analysis and its principles, conclusions, studied economic laws and categories serve as a methodological basis for other socio-economic branches, special sciences.

Therefore, it should be noted that in the system of economic sciences, along with "*economic theory*", there are also special professional sciences, in which economic issues are studied more widely, these are:

- Sciences of economic history (history of economic doctrines, history of national economy, history of the economy of countries, etc.);

- Branched economic sciences (industrial economy, agricultural economy, construction economy, tourism economy, etc.);

- Special subjects (finance, statistics, marketing, management, business basics, etc.). Each of these directions combines dozens of scientific disciplines with theoretical and practical sections;

4) ideological-educational task - with the help of this task, students, experts form the worldview of economics students (contemporary economic thinking, modern market) [3].

The purpose of "Economic theory" science is to formulate economic problems and ways to solve them, as an economic theoretical basis, the policy of any state. However, the existence of economic policy without "Economic Theory" is unthinkable. Consequently, economic theory studies the economic behavior of people. Therefore, this science is a humanitarian (social) science. Therefore, the economic policy of any state is based on the theory of economics, which studies objective laws in society in modern conditions. In this case, it is impossible to imagine the activity of the medical field without economic knowledge, of course. Especially in the current market economy.

It is no secret that since the years of independence in our country, the teaching of economic theory has been stopped in non-economic higher educational institutions and specialties, as well as in the training of medical personnel. Therefore, for more than thirty years of our country's independence, personnel have been trained for the process of building the market economy "Uzbek model", but during this period, our personnel trained in non-economic higher educational institutions of our country were not given economic knowledge. Because economic theory is not in the curriculum.

Why? Perhaps the "leaders of the country" were too greedy financially to spend hours teaching economic theory to these students, or perhaps they confused the importance of economic theory in training "good" personnel? Is there no need for economic knowledge?

Of course, it's a pity, think about today's education, how can a new specialist with different profiles be trained in accordance with market requirements without obtaining economic knowledge? After all, market relations (private property) are widespread in all spheres of economic life, in particular, in production and services, including education, health care, and others! How can a specialist operate in a market economy without economic knowledge?

As it turns out, the main reason for this problem is that, in the conditions of the beginning of the transition to the market, our "managers" did not sufficiently evaluate the place, role and importance of economic theory in the process of formation and development of the market economy. At this point, it would be appropriate to mention the following, that is, if we look at the history of our country, even in the period of socialism, economic education - "political economy" was taught compulsorily in the training of personnel in all specialties. It seems that "no one" paid attention to the importance of this history.

In accordance with this, in the coming years in our country, according to the joint program of training of medical personnel established with the leading medical higher education institutions of Russia: economic theory, economics, financial literacy, management and marketing sciences will be taught to students (in Russian). I wonder why these subjects are still not included in our national medical personnel training program. Is the experience of Russia and other countries not used in this matter? Or are we lagging behind in this area?

After all, as we are building a socially oriented market economy, according to the demand of the market economy, our future personnel should thoroughly acquire economic knowledge. For this purpose, the subject of economic theory should be added to the curriculum of all specialties being prepared, and economic education should be widely introduced. We believe that this is the requirement of the present time.

Currently, the medical field is facing a number of challenges related to budget constraints, cost of technology and drugs, establishment of a medical facility, and provision of quality medical care. To function successfully in this environment, health care workers must understand economic thinking and the principles of health economics.

Knowledge of economic aspects can help health professionals make informed decisions to optimize the use of resources and provide quality care. They must consider the cost of drugs, medical equipment, and evaluate the effectiveness of various techniques and procedures. Economic knowledge allows you to analyze costs and benefits and choose the best ways to achieve the desired result.

Competition in the medical market also determines the demand for economic knowledge of medical workers. To be successful, doctors and nurses need to know how to develop and optimize their practice, and how to attract and retain more patients. Economic knowledge will help you understand the principles of marketing, financial planning and business management, which will allow you to develop your medical practice or be more in demand and successful in the labor market [4].

Socialization is one of the conditions for the competitiveness of a medical university graduate in the labor market. It helps the future specialist to be optimally involved in socio-economic relations in the society, his successful adaptation and integration into the dynamic market environment. In the process of socialization, students acquire the skills of assessing different situations, rational behavior, effective interpersonal communication and joint activity. The most important processes of forming the personality of a future specialist at a medical university are socialization related to mastering the social role of a doctor, whose professional activity is characterized by a high level of responsibility.

A social role is a model of behavior that corresponds to a certain status in a certain social system. The doctor has a special status as the main element of the health care system. The important role of the doctor in society is determined by the value of health.

All this is to realize the importance of economic knowledge. They allow to ensure the process of economic socialization by obtaining a theoretical system, economic knowledge that helps to develop economic culture, enable adequate interaction in the current environmental conditions, reality, the ability to correctly interpret socio-economic processes, including:

- economic relations that develop objectively in the course of medicine, professional activity (providing medical care);
- forms and manifestations of economic laws in the field of health care;

- the economic nature of the use of resources in health care.

Economic knowledge, which is in demand in the practical work of a doctor, is formed in the process of mastering such subjects as economics (economic theory), health economics, etc. during university studies.

About the professional, the doctor's activity, which includes a high level of responsibility, then the development of economic thinking is a necessary condition for the full formation of his personal and professional qualities, professional competences.

Economic socialization allows for the formation of a relatively stable type of rational economic behavior directed at the real values of life. One of the characteristics of the psychological state of the doctor is the feeling of being an active subject of economic relations, including understanding of socio-economic relations. Conditionality of health problems, economic conditions of quality are the services provided, characteristics of the labor market, etc. [6].

Therefore, in the Concept of the health care system of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the years 2019-2025, it is envisaged to increase the role of the private sector by attracting investments in the medical field, but economic knowledge in training, retraining and upgrading the skills of highly qualified medical personnel nothing is said about [2].

Therefore, according to the ideological and educational function of the theory of economics, it forms the current economic thinking of future experts, the general public, students of economics, and the outlook on the market. Moreover, the idea of national independence of our country is inculcated in the minds of students and young people, they are encouraged to develop the economy in the direction of national interests, to increase the national product, to increase the value of our national currency, to ensure the global demand for national goods, and to raise the standard of living of the country's population. educates in spirit.

Also, this science forms a business mindset in the future medical personnel who are entering an independent life, by acquiring financial literacy, entrepreneurial skills and secrets, and serves as the main foundation for the development of new entrepreneurs and representatives of business management. of course.

It must be said that in some higher education, subjects such as "Medical economy", "management-marketing" are taught, this cannot be denied. The fundamental basis of these sciences is the science of economic theory. There is no doubt about this opinion [6]. However, in this process, the theory of economics was ignored in medical universities of Uzbekistan. Pedagogical experience shows that its effect is almost non-existent. Because it is necessary to start teaching from the theory of economics, which is the fundamental basis of these sciences. However, we believe that using them in the educational process without knowing the true essence of economic categories and laws from economic theory is an ineffective attempt.

Therefore, it is difficult to imagine the training of highly qualified medical specialists in modern times without basic economic knowledge. Therefore, teaching the science of economic theory in the higher education system is an urgent issue not only in the training of economists, but also in the training of highly qualified specialists in all non-economic areas, as well as in medicine.

Conclusion and proposal: Based on all these points, it should be concluded that the demand of market relations in today's economy requires that the subject of "Economic Theory" be taught in medical universities of our country in all specialties. We propose to include philosophy, modern history of Uzbekistan, religious studies as a compulsory subject in the curriculum. However, we must not forget that we are preparing future personnel for the market economy.

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